

AN INDICATOR OF THE INFLUENCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EVERY SPHERE OF LIFE

Akhatova Dilshoda Bakhodir kizi

Student of Denau Institute Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

ahadovbexrur@gmail.com

Annotation: This article explores the advantages and disadvantages of artificial intelligence, as well as the impact of artificial intelligence on youth. Artificial intelligence is one of the most important directions of modern technologies. It can reproduce human analytical skills and greatly helps in data processing and analysis. AI drives innovation in the economy, health, education, and many other areas. However, ethical and safety issues related to its growing role also remain relevant. This technology needs to be managed carefully.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, consciousness, advantages and disadvantages robots, youth humans, problems, solutions.

Artificial intelligence is a program that helps a person to think and create ideas for all the things that a person needs to think and do. Today, in any corner of the world, we can see that artificial intelligence and we can see it has become part of it is life. Although artificial intelligence has useful properties, and also has negative aspects. Currently, artificial intelligence is rapidly developing around the world. Artificial intelligence is very helpful when we face difficult problems and understand the issues that are difficult for us to understand and also to find solutions for environmental problems. In addition, artificial intelligence helps in understanding mathematical, physical, and chemical problems and examples.

Despite the advantages of artificial intelligence, it also has it is disadvantages. First of all, applications that work with mobile communications and artificial intelligence are harmful to human health. Artificial intelligence has captured people's minds so much that people are even turning to this app to perform simple tasks. The rapid development of artificial intelligence has the potential to solve previously unsolvable problems, cure diseases, agree, environmental issues, and even help us understand the human mind.

One of the applications that is widely used and used by the general public is CHATGPT. People are so attached to this application that they do not want to solve anything with their thinking and minds. In the prestigious universities of America,

from this application, the result of the political processes taking place in the country and what will happen next and used to find out about the causes. There is only one question that worries me, urges me to find a solution, and asks me to know the reason. We create applications, mechanisms, programs, and robots but we have not yet realized that they are controlling us, not them. We have allowed our programming to control our minds. But we have forgotten that programming is only made for difficult situations. If robots take the place of humans in developing countries, why should something created by humans oppose themselves?

In the right education system, this application has the advantages. For example, every student can study subjects that are difficult for him to understand, learn a language through various language teaching applications, and earn money through some applications.

Also, if someone wants to learn a language, they can learn and memorize it through various free apps. As artificial intelligence continues to grow and develop, it is important to understand it is the potential impact on the education sector, both positive and negative. The advantages of artificial intelligence in education. One major advantage is the ability to personalize learning for each student. Artificial intelligence-powered learning platforms can gather data on each student's learning style and pace also, adopt the curriculum to fit their needs. This means that students can learn at their own pace and in a way that is most effective for them. Another advantage is the ability to free up time for teachers. Artificial intelligence can automate tasks such as grading assignments and providing feedback, allowing teachers focus on more important tasks such as lesson planning and student engagement.

Artificial intelligence has some disadvantages, we should not forget them. With every technology there are also potential disadvantages. One concern is the possibility of bias in artificial intelligence algorithms. Students and teachers. If teachers mistakenly enter student grades and midterms into the Hemis program, it is very difficult to correct this process, and correcting it will cause several problems.

Artificial intelligence has another troubling side. Shortly, artificial intelligence, which is becoming a part of people's lives, is also taking over people's work, that is their professions. Let's imagine that if we get all the help from this program for free and without anyone's help if we stick to it, we can cause the disappearance of some professions. Also, this process will not affect the education system. Students and teachers. If teachers mistakenly enter student grades and midterms into the Hemis program, it is very difficult to correct this process, and correcting it will cause some

problems. By embracing artificial intelligence as a tool rather than a replacement staying informed, and focusing on the human element of education.

We can ensure that the future of education is bright and inclusive for all. When you use these apps regularly or ask even easy things, this app will start occupying your mind. You will become lazy and lazy. It is appropriate for a person to use these applications when making judgments about issues that are difficult to find a solution in the political society. If artificial intelligence is used a lot, the human brain will be inhibited and it will be difficult to think about simple things and draw conclusions on them. Because the application will then become a part of the person, 100% of the human brain and memory work, why do we have to think about things for ourselves we upload to applications? Is it because of the convenience or are there any superior aspects of the applications? Of course, because of the ease, the person who created this application means that the person is smarter and more thoughtful than the application. Using applications at the right time is useful for everyone.

Before applications take the place of people, we should understand that these applications are just tools, we should not let various programs take over our minds and find solutions to all problems and difficult situations by ourselves. After all, people are 1000 times smarter, more thoughtful, and more experienced than applications. We need to stop getting attached to apps and understand why we need them.

References:

1. Bostrom, N. (2014). The future of artificial intelligence. Machine Intelligence Research Institute.
2. Kelly, K. (2016). Artificial intelligence: You and robots. Wired.
3. Hassabis, D. (n.d.). New possibilities of artificial intelligence. Nature and Science.
4. Harari, Y. N. (2015). Homo Deus: A brief history of tomorrow.